

**RAYAT-BAHRA
UNIVERSITY**

PURSUE YOUR DREAMS

EURO-ASIAN CONFERENCE

ON

Sustainable Nanotechnology, Environment, & Energy (SNE2-2024)

Organized by

Research & Incubation Centre

Rayat Bahra University, Mohali, Punjab, India

in association with

**National University of Singapore, University of Salento, Italy &
University of Montpellier, France**

Join us

 15th - 16th October, 2024

HYBRID MODE

Contact us

Website:- www.snee.rayatbahrauniversity.edu.in, Email:- snee@rayatbahrauniversity.edu.in, Mob:- +91-83604 65146

ORGANIZING COMMITTEE

CHIEF PATRON

S. Gurvinder Singh Bahra
Honourable Chairman, Rayat Bahra Group
Honourable Chancellor,
Rayat Bahra University, Mohali, Punjab, India

PATRON

S. Gurinder Singh Bahra
Vice Chairman
Rayat Bahra Group

CO- PATRON (s)

Prof.(Dr.) Satbir Singh Sehgal
Vice President
Rayat Bahra Group

Prof.(Dr.) Parvinder Singh
Honourable Vice - Chancellor
Rayat Bahra University, Mohali, Punjab, India

CONFERENCE MENTOR (s)

Prof.(Dr.) Dinesh Sharma
Registrar
Rayat Bahra University, Mohali, Punjab, India

Prof.(Dr.) Satish Kumar Bansal
Dean Academic Affairs
Rayat Bahra University, Mohali, Punjab, India

CONFERENCE CHAIR (s)

Prof.(Dr.) Raman Kumar
Director, Research & Incubation
Rayat Bahra University, Mohali, Punjab, India

Prof.(Dr.) Maninder Singh
Director, Research
Rayat Bahra University, Mohali, Punjab, India

Prof.(Dr.) Jasgurpreet Singh Chohan
Director, Entrepreneurship
Rayat Bahra University, Mohali, Punjab, India

Event Management Incharge

Mr. B.S Bains
Director, Administration
Rayat Bahra University, Mohali, Punjab, India

IT Team

Dr. Divya Bahl
Director, IT
Rayat Bahra University, Mohali, Punjab, India

Ms. Barjinder Kaur
Rayat Bahra University, Mohali, Punjab, India

CONFERENCE CONVENER

Prof. Jagpreet Singh
Assistant Director, Research Publications
Rayat Bahra University, Mohali

CONFERENCE CO-CONVENER (s)

Prof. Manoj Gupta
Provost's Chair, College of Design and Engineering
National University of Singapore, Singapore

Prof. Mikhael Bechelany
Director, Research, CNRS
European Institute of Membranes, Montpellier, France

Dr. Valeria De Matteis
University of Salento, Italy

CONFERENCE SECRETARIAT (s)

Prof.(Dr.) Manoj Bali
Dean, University School of Sciences
Rayat Bahra University, Mohali, Punjab, India

Prof.(Dr.) Anju Goyal
Dean, University School of Pharmaceutical Sciences
Rayat Bahra University, Mohali, Punjab, India

PUBLICATION CHAIR (s)

Dr. Monika Bhattu
Assistant Professor, Research,
Rayat Bahra University, Mohali, Punjab, India

Prof.(Dr.) Daniela Šojić Merkulov
Department of Chemistry,
Biochemistry and Environmental Protection
University of Novi Sad, SERBIA

FINANCE CHAIR

Mr. Arun Jain
CFO,
Rayat Bahra University, Mohali, Punjab, India

Marketing & Communication

Mr. Saurabh Sharma
Director- Branding
Rayat Bahra University, Mohali, Punjab, India

ADVISORY BOARD

Prof.(Dr.) David Cornu

Ecole Nationale Supérieure de Chimie de Montpellier (ENSCM, France)
Institut Européen des Membranes (IEM)

Prof.(Dr.) Julien Cambedouzou

Ecole Nationale Supérieure de Chimie de Montpellier

Prof.(Dr.) Loris Rizzello

University of Milan, Italy

Dr. Belgin SEVER

Associate Professor
Anadolu University Faculty of Pharmacy
Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, 26470 Eskişehir / Turkey

Prof. (Dr.) Mika Sillanpaa

Florida International University

Dr. Joanna Feder-Kubis

Associate Professor
Wroclaw University of Science and Technology, Poland

Dr. Jithendra Panneerselvam

International Medical University, Malaysia

Dr Sedigheh (Marzieh) Ghadamgahi

Director
Nanotechnology Center,
Azad University, Tehran, Iran

Dr. Mohammed J.K. Bashir

School of Engineering and Technology,
Tertiary Education Division,
Central Queensland University, Melbourne, Australia

Dr. Kuan Shiong Khoo

Department of Chemical Engineering and Materials Science,
Yuan Ze University, Taoyuan, Taiwan.

Dr. B. Ravindran

Associate Professor
Department of Environmental Energy & Engineering,
Kyonggi University, Republic of Korea.

Prof.(Dr.) Soumen Basu

Thapar University, Punjab, India

Dr. Sameh Samir Ali

Botany Department, Faculty of Science,
Tanta University, Tanta, 31527, Egypt

Dr. Vanish Saini

Assistant Professor
Thapar University, Punjab, India

Dr. Nina Finčur

Assistant Professor
Department of Chemistry, Biochemistry and
Environmental Protection Trg Dositeja Obradovića 3, SERBIA

Prof.(Dr.) Andres Moreno

Catedrático in Organic Chemistry
Universidad de Castilla-La Mancha, SPAIN

Dr. Afzal Ahmad Dar

Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering,
Concordia University, Montreal Canada.

Prof.(Dr.) Rajender S. Varma

USEPA, USA
Czech Advanced Technology and Research Institute,
Palacky University, Czech Republic

Dr. Mariafrancesca Cascione

Assistant Professor
University of Salento, Lecce, Italy

Dr. Sebastin Raveendar

Department of Industrial Plant Science and Technology,
Chungbuk National University, Cheongju, South Korea

Dr. Akansha Mehta

Researcher
Alexander Dubcek University of Trencin, Slovakia

Dr. Muhammad Fahad Sardar

School of Life Science, Shandong University, Qingdao China

Prof.(Dr.) Ebru Bozkurt

Program of Occupational Health and Safety,
Vocational College of Technical Sciences,
Atatürk University, 25240, Erzurum, Turkey

Prof.(Dr.) Ghodsi Mohammadi Ziarani

Department of Organic Chemistry
Alzahra University, Tehran, Iran

Prof. (Dr.) Md Enamul Hoque

Department of Biomedical Engineering
Military Institute of Science and Technology
Dhaka, Bangladesh

Dr. Muhammad Anwaar Nazeer

Assistant Professor
National Textile University, Pakistan.

Dr, Karanpal Singh

Indian Institute of Technology, Kanpur, India

Dr. Damandeep Kaur

Postdoc researcher at MIPLAB (MICRODEVICES FOR
PHOTONICS LABORATORY) Institute of Applied Physics-CNR,
Florence, Italy

EURO-ASIA CONFERENCE ON SUSTAINABLE NANOTECHNOLOGY, ENVIRONMENT, AND ENERGY (SNE2-2024)

Instructions

1. The presenter's allotted time for presentation is 10 min with 2 mins of Q & A.
2. The audience to keep their cams and audio off. Also, any question from the audience is typed into the classroom chat which will be taken up by the session chair to the presenter after the presentation.
3. All presenters within the time slot i.e., before lunch or post-lunch to be available online as anyone can be called upon for presentation to avoid unnecessary delays.
4. The session chair will indicate the presenter using an alarm (Use mobile alarm) through AUDIO regarding the presentation time left (at 8 mins) without interrupting the presenter.
5. All decisions of the session lie within the jurisdiction of the session chairs.

Technical Session 1 (DAY-1); October 15th, 2024

Keynote Speaker : Prof. (Dr) Volker Hessel; The University of Adelaide, Australia

Session Chair: Dr. Belgin SEVER ; Anadolu University Turkey

Zoom Meeting Link:

<https://us06web.zoom.us/j/89869315547?pwd=Zo3nFmWCvpBHdDGf26omsodzN50zwz.1>

Meeting ID: 898 6931 5547 ; Passcode: 200965

Keynote Speaker 11:30 PM to 12:00 PM;

S. No.	Presenter Name	Paper Title	SLOT	Timing (IST)
1.	Sonali Goyal	Efficient Desulfurization of Light Crude Oil Using MOF and its composite.	Post-Lunch	12:00-12:10 pm
2.	DuÅ¼ica JovanoviÄ	ZnO-based coatings in solar-enhanced removal of ciprofloxacin from the aqueous medium		12:10-12:20 pm
3.	Paolo Pellegrino	Antibacterial Properties of PMMA Nanograting and Nanopillar Arrays: An AFM Analysis		12:20-12:30 pm
4.	Szabolcs BognÄr	Advancing sustainable nanotechnology: Green synthesis of ZnO nanomaterials for photocatalytic degradation of organics in water		12:30-12:40 pm
5.	Subham Chakraborty	Measuring of Surface Roughness of Al-6061 Alloy by CNC Milling by using of Taguchi Method		12:40-12:50 pm
6.	Laura Maria Slavu	Bimetal nanoparticles based Cu@Au nanozyme as promising nanomaterials for enhanced sensitive lateral flow assay (LFAs)		12:50-01:00 pm
7.	Anu Radha Pathania	Comparative analysis of glimepiride interactions with bovine serum albumin and fibrinogen using fluorescence spectroscopy		01:00-01:10 pm
8.	Annalisa Bianco	Green synthesis of Chitosan Nanoparticles as Locked Nucleic Acid Delivery Systems		01:10-01:20 pm
9.	Batchu Ramanajneyulu	Transforming Treacherous Terrains: Enhancing Black Cotton Soil Stability with Calcium Lignosulfonate and Marble Dust		01:20-01:30 pm
10.	Sajal Rai	Investigations on melt flow index of orange peel powder reinforced thermoplastic composites for fdm filament fabrication		

Advancing sustainable nanotechnology: Green synthesis of ZnO nanomaterials for photocatalytic degradation of organics in water

Szabolcs Bognár^{1*}, Dušica Jovanović¹, Sanja Panić², Vesna Despotović¹, Nina Finčur¹, and Daniela Šojić Merkulov¹

¹University of Novi Sad Faculty of Sciences, Department of Chemistry, Biochemistry and Environmental Protection, Trg Dositeja Obradovića 3, 21000 Novi Sad, Serbia

²University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technology Novi Sad, Bulevar cara Lazara 1, 21000 Novi Sad, Serbia

Abstract. The environmental pollution, especially pure water scarcity, is an eager problem in the modern society. Various organic pollutants (e.g. drugs, pesticides) are found in the aquatic environment, which cannot be removed by conventional water treatment techniques. Heterogeneous photocatalysis, one of the advanced oxidation processes, showed high efficiency in the removal of organics. This process employs nanomaterials as photocatalysts and renewable solar irradiation. The aim of this research was to develop a novel approach to the green synthesis of ZnO nanoparticles using banana peel (ZnO/BPE) and green tea extracts, under various synthesis settings. The novel ZnO nanomaterials were tested in the photocatalytic degradation of two critical organic pollutants: tembotrione (TEM), a herbicide, and 17 α -ethynilestradiol (EE2), an endocrine-disrupting compound, applying solar irradiation under different experimental conditions. Furthermore, the photocatalytic activity of pure banana peel extract was also investigated. The confirmed high photocatalytic activity of the newly synthesized nanomaterials makes them suitable for the removal of TEM and EE2 from aqueous environment, under solar irradiation. On the other hand, the pure banana peel extract exhibited better efficiency than the novel ZnO/BPE nanomaterial. The findings suggest that integrating plant extracts in nanotechnology can lead to sustainable, high-performance solutions for water treatment and pollution control.

Acknowledgment. This research was funded by the Science Fund of the Republic of Serbia (Grant No. 7747845, *In situ* pollutants removal from waters by sustainable green nanotechnologies-CleanNanoCatalyze) and by the Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation of the Republic of Serbia (Grant Numbers 451-03-66/2024-03/200125 and 451-03-65/2024-03/200125).

*Corresponding author: sabolc.bognar@dh.uns.ac.rs

**RAYAT-BAHRA
UNIVERSITY**
PURSUE YOUR DREAMS

Certificate of Oral Presentation

EURO-ASIAN CONFERENCE ON SUSTAINABLE NANOTECHNOLOGY, ENVIRONMENT & ENERGY (SNEE-2024)

This is to Certify that Mr./Ms. Szabolcs Bognair from University of Novi Sad Faculty of Sciences, Serbia
has presented a paper entitled” Advancing sustainable nanotechnology: Green synthesis of ZnO nanomaterials for
photocatalytic degradation of organics in water

at “EURO-ASIAN CONFERENCE ON SUSTAINABLE NANOTECHNOLOGY, ENVIRONMENT & ENERGY (SNEE-2024)” Organized by
Research & Incubation Centre, Rayat Bahra University, Punjab, India in association with the National University of Singapore,
University of Salento, Italy & University of Montpellier, France on 15 -16th October 2024.

Jagpreet Singh
Conference Convenor
Rayat Bahra University

Raman Kumar
Director, Research & Incubation
Rayat Bahra University